

ESM C

Items Selected Items from GESIS Panel and Items Derived During Preprocessing

Name	Label	Kind / type of concept	Incl.	RfE	VIF
a11d054a	Sex	Sociodemographic	Yes		1.83
bfzh069a	Sex	Sociodemographic	No	T	
a11d056b	Age	Sociodemographic	Yes		1.89
bfzh070c	Age	Sociodemographic	No	T	
a11d057d	Citizenship of respondent	Sociodemographic	Yes		1.29
bfzh071a	German citizenship	Sociodemographic	No	T	
bfzh072a	Foreign citizenship	Sociodemographic	No	T	
a11d072d	Country of birth	Sociodemographic	No	S	
a11d075d	Country of birth mother	Sociodemographic	No	S	
a11d077d	Country of birth father	Sociodemographic	No	S	
a11d079b	Marital status	Sociodemographic	No	S	
bfzh073b	Marital status	Sociodemographic	No	T	
a11d080a	Steady partner	Sociodemographic	No	S	
bfzh074a	Steady partner	Sociodemographic	No	NA	
a11d081a	Joint household	Sociodemographic	No	NA	
bfzh075a	Joint household	Sociodemographic	No	NA	
a11d093b	Household size	Sociodemographic	Yes		2.04
bfzh084a	Household size, one or more persons	Sociodemographic	No	T	

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bfzh085c	Household size, more than one person	Sociodemographic	No	T	
a11d094a	Children under 16 years	Sociodemographic	Yes		2.05
a11d095b	Number of Children under 16 years	Sociodemographic	No	NA	
bfzh086a	Children under 16 years in household, yes/no	Sociodemographic	No	T	
bfzh087c	Number of Children under 16 years	Sociodemographic	No	T	
bfar042a	Cohesion inside family	Value	No	T	
bfar043a	Number of generations inside household	Sociodemographic	No	T	
a12d021b	Federal state, east/west, geographical	Sociodemographic	Yes		.128
a12c023a	Quality of life in region	Quality of life	Yes		1.34
a12c025a	Affected by environmental influences: noise pollution	Quality of life	No	M	
bczd002a	Exposure to environmental hazards: noise pollution	Quality of life	No	S	
a12c026a	Affected by environmental influences: air pollution	Quality of life	No	M	
bczd003a	Affected by environmental influences: air pollution	Quality of life	No	S	
a12c027a	Affected by environmental influences: missing accessible public parks	Quality of life	No	M	
bczd004a	Exposure to environmental hazards: lack of green space	Quality of life	Yes		1.38
bczd001a	Distance between residential area and large city	Sociodemographic	Yes		1.21
a11d082b	Highest level of education	Sociodemographic	No	S	
bfzh076a	Highest level of education	Sociodemographic	No	T	
a11d086b	Vocational or professional training	Sociodemographic	No	S	
bfzh082a	Professional degree	Sociodemographic	No	T	

Name	Label	Kind / type of concept	Incl.	RfE	VIF
bfzh079a	University degree	Sociodemographic	No	T	
bfzh080a	Type of university degree	Sociodemographic	No	T	
a11d096b	Personal net income	Financial situation	Yes		2.34
bfzh088b	Personal net income	Financial situation	No	T	
a11d097c	Household net income	Financial situation	Yes		2.09
bfzh089c	Household net income	Financial situation	No	T	
bbak116a	Financial situation household today, compared with 12 months ago	Financial situation	Yes		1.36
bbak117a	Financial situation household future	Financial situation	Yes		1.41
bbak118a	Assessment financial situation household	Financial situation	No	E	
bdao099a	Subjective class affiliation	Sociodemographic	Yes		1.68
bazb012a	Importance: financial situation	Value	Yes		.142
bazb018a	Satisfaction: Financial Situation	Financial situation	Yes		1.64
a12c008a	Satisfaction economic situation in Germany	Economy, perception	No	M	
bbak111a	Satisfaction state of the economy in Germany	Economy, perception	Yes		1.60
bbak113a	Reduce differences in income levels	Value	No	O	
bbak114a	Economic situation today, compared with 12 months ago	Economy, perception	Yes		1.44
bbak115a	Economic situation future	Economy, perception	Yes		1.51
bbaj093a	Worried: paying household bills	Quality of life	No	S	
bbaj094a	Worried: reduce standard of living	Quality of life	No	S	
bbaj095a	Worried: having a job	Quality of life	Yes		1.73

Name	Label	Kind / type of concept	Incl.	RfE	VIF
bbaj096a	Worried: paying of bank loans or mortgage payments	Quality of life	No	S	
a11c021a	Satisfaction life in general	Quality of life	No	M	
bazb004a	Satisfaction with previous course of life	Quality of life	No	S	
bazb005a	Current satisfaction with life	Quality of life	No	M	
bcan111a	Current satisfaction with life	Quality of life	No	M	
bdan124a	Current satisfaction with life	Quality of life	No	M	
bean147a	Current satisfaction with life	Quality of life	No	S	
bazb006a	Satisfaction in a year from now	Quality of life	No	S	
bbak098a	Life satisfaction	Quality of life	No	S	
bezg088a	Job satisfaction	Quality of life	No	NA	
bezg117a	Satisfaction leisure time	Quality of life	No	O	
bbak099a	Current happiness	Quality of life	No	M	
bcan110a	Current happiness	Quality of life	No	M	
bdan123a	Current happiness	Quality of life	No	M	
bean146a	Current happiness	Quality of life	No	S	
a11c022a	Trust: general trust	Trait	No	M	
bbzc088a	General trust	Trait	No	O	
a11c025a	Standard of living young generation	Economy, perception	No	S	
bbzc022a	Frequency political news	Politics	No	O	
a12c009a	Political interest	Politics	No	M	
bbzc001a	Political interest	Politics	Yes		1.54

Name	Label	Kind / type of concept	Incl.	RfE	VIF
a12c010a	Left-right scale	Politics	No	M	
bcaj055a	Left-right self-classification	Politics	Yes		1.45
a12c012a	Civic duty: not evade taxes	Attitude	No	M	
a12c015a	Civic duty: social/political activity	Attitude	Yes		1.41
a12c017a	Civic duty: political consume	Attitude	Yes		1.49
bbzc071a	Norms of citizenship: show solidarity	Value	Yes		1.38
bbzc073a	Norms of citizenship: never evade taxes	Value	Yes		1.24
baah118a	Climate change	Attitude	No	S	
baah119a	Climate change	Attitude	No	S	
baah143a	Experiment variable: climate change	Attitude	No	S	
bczd034a	Climate protection policy pace	Attitude	Yes		1.62
bczd035a	Seriousness of climate change problem	Attitude	Yes		1.35
a11c110a	Emotions work: confident	Quality of life	No	NA	
a12c053a	Ideal occupation: high income	Attitude	Yes		1.52
a12c062a	Ideal occupation: useful for society	Attitude	Yes		1.37
a12c063a	Personal priority: be able to afford something	Attitude	Yes		1.44
a12c070a	Personal priority: campaign politically/socially	Attitude	Yes		1.58
beaq127a	Weekly market: regional groceries	Purchase intention and motivation	No	O, NA	
beaq128a	Weekly market: organic produce	Purchase intention and motivation	No	O, NA	

Name	Label	Kind / type of concept	Incl.	RfE	VIF
beaq129a	Weekly market: groceries too expensive	Attitude	No	NA	
beaq130a	Weekly market: limited choice of products	Attitude	No	O, NA	
beaq131a	Weekly market: hard to reach	Attitude	No	O	
beaq132a	Weekly market: high quality produce	Attitude	No	O, NA	
beaq133a	Likelihood of shopping at a weekly market during next four weeks	Purchase intention and motivation	No	O	
beaq134a	Shopping at weekly markets, positive reinforcement family	Attitude third party	No	O	
beaq135a	Shopping at weekly markets, positive reinforcement friends	Attitude third party	No	NA	
beaq136a	Having a good feeling when buying local produce	Purchase intention and motivation	No	O	
beaq137a	Likelihood organic produce next shopping trip	Purchase intention and motivation	No	S	
beaq138a	Organic produce too expensive	Attitude	No	O	
beaq139a	Positive contribution to environment when buying organic produce	Attitude	No	S	
beaq140a	Good feeling when buying organic produce	Attitude	No	S	
beaq144a	Environmentally friendly investment, positive feedback friends	Attitude third party	No	NA	
beaq145a	Environmentally friendly investment, positive feedback family	Attitude third party	No	NA	
bczd020a	Willingness to pay environment: higher prices	Attitude	Yes		1.99
bczd021a	Willingness to pay environment: higher taxes	Attitude	Yes		1.68
bczd022a	Willingness to pay environment: cut standard of living	Attitude	Yes		1.62
bczd043a	Purchase organic groceries	Purchase intention and motivation	No	M	

Name	Label	Kind / type of concept	Incl.	RfE	VIF
		motivation			
bczd044a	Purchase regional food	Purchase intention and motivation	No	E	
bczd045a	Purchase green energy	Purchase intention and motivation	Yes		1.23
bfar031a	Taxable inheritance right	Attitude	No	T	
bfar032a	Inheritance tax break for caretaker	Attitude	No	T	
bfar033a	Early transferral of assets	Attitude	No	T	
bfar034a	Ricardian equivalence: increasing savings	Attitude	No	T	
bfar035a	Life does not change after receiving inheritance	Attitude	No	T	
bfar036a	Attitude seed money	Attitude	No	T	
bfar040a	Estimated inheritance tax at 100 000 €	Attitude	No	T	
bfar041a	Estimated inheritance tax at 1 000 000 €	Attitude	No	T	
bbal119a	PANAS: active	Affective experience	No	S	
bbal120a	PANAS: distressed	Affective experience	No	S	
bbal121a	PANAS: interested	Affective experience	No	S	
bbal122a	PANAS: elated	Affective experience	No	S	
bbal123a	PANAS: upset	Affective experience	No	S	
bbal124a	PANAS: strong	Affective experience	No	S	
bbal125a	PANAS: guilty	Affective experience	No	S	
bbal126a	PANAS: terrified	Affective experience	No	S	

Name	Label	Kind / type of concept	Incl.	RfE	VIF
bbal127a	PANAS: hostile	Affective experience	No	S	
bbal128a	PANAS: stimulated	Affective experience	No	S	
bbal129a	PANAS: proud	Affective experience	No	S	
bbal130a	PANAS: irritable	Affective experience	No	S	
bbal131a	PANAS: excited	Affective experience	No	S	
bbal132a	PANAS: ashamed	Affective experience	No	S	
bbal133a	PANAS: awake	Affective experience	No	S	
bbal134a	PANAS: nervous	Affective experience	No	S	
bbal135a	PANAS: determined	Affective experience	No	S	
bbal136a	PANAS: attentive	Affective experience	No	S	
bbal137a	PANAS: confused	Affective experience	No	S	
bbal138a	PANAS: anxious	Affective experience	No	S	
bczd005a	NEP-Scale: approaching maximum number of humans	Attitude	No	S	
bczd006a	NEP-Scale: right to adapt environment to the needs	Attitude	No	S	
bczd007a	NEP-Scale: consequences of human intervention	Attitude	No	S	
bczd008a	NEP-Scale: human ingenuity	Attitude	No	S	
bczd009a	NEP-Scale: abuse of the environment by humans	Attitude	No	S	
bczd010a	NEP-Scale: sufficient natural resources	Attitude	No	S	
bczd011a	NEP-Scale: equal rights for plants and animals	Attitude	No	S	
bczd012a	NEP-Scale: balance of nature stable enough	Attitude	No	S	
bczd013a	NEP-Scale: humans are subject to natural laws	Attitude	No	S	

Name	Label	Kind / type of concept	Incl.	RfE	VIF
bczd014a	NEP-Scale: environmental crisis greatly exaggerated	Attitude	No	S	
bczd015a	NEP-Scale: earth is like spaceship	Attitude	No	S	
bczd016a	NEP-Scale: humans were assigned to rule over nature	Attitude	No	S	
bczd017a	NEP-Scale: balance of nature is very sensitive	Attitude	No	S	
bczd018a	NEP-Scale: control nature	Attitude	No	S	
bczd019a	NEP-Scale: environmental disaster	Attitude	No	S	
bdze001a	BFI-10: rather reserved	Trait	No	S	
bdze002a	BFI-10: easily trust people	Trait	No	S	
bdze003a	BFI-10: rather lazy	Trait	No	S	
bdze004a	BFI-10: relaxed	Trait	No	S	
bdze005a	BFI-10: only little artistic interest	Trait	No	S	
bdze006a	BFI-10: communicative and socialable	Trait	No	S	
bdze007a	BFI-10: tend to criticise others	Trait	No	S	
bdze008a	BFI-10: accomplish tasks effectively	Trait	No	S	
bdze009a	BFI-10: easily become nervous	Trait	No	S	
bdze010a	BFI-10: have lively fantasies	Trait	No	S	
bdze011a	Values: take care of nature	Value	No	S	
bdze012a	Values: show that own achievements are better	Value	No	S	
bdze013a	Values: always form own opinion	Value	No	S	
bdze014a	Values: preserve traditional values and convictions	Value	No	S	
bdze015a	Values: be tolerant towards other people and social groups	Value	No	S	

Name	Label	Kind / type of concept	Incl.	RfE	VIF
bdze016a	Values: be rich	Value	No	S	
bdze017a	Values: live in a strong state	Value	No	S	
bdze018a	Values: expand knowledge	Value	No	S	
bdze019a	Values: help people who matter to him/her	Value	No	S	
bdze020a	Values: gain new experiences	Value	No	S	
bdze021a	Values: tell other people what to do	Value	No	S	
bdze022a	Values: obey the law	Value	No	S	
bdze023a	Values: take care of the needs of people	Value	No	S	
bdze024a	Values: have the freedom to choose what to do	Value	No	S	
bdze025a	Values: others recognise his/her achievements	Value	No	S	
bdze026a	Values: all people are treated fairly	Value	No	S	
bdze027a	Values: get to the bottom of things	Value	No	S	
climate_change	Climate Change	Attitude	Yes		1.10
standard_young	Future standard of life young generation	Economy, perception	Yes		1.13
relationship_status	Relationship status	Sociodemographic	Yes		1.20
school_deg	Highest school leaving certificate	Sociodemographic	Yes		2.12
job_deg	Vocational or professional training	Sociodemographic	Yes		2.00
bfi10_extraversion	BFI-10: Extraversion	Trait	Yes		1.35
bfi10_openness	BFI-10: Openness	Trait	Yes		1.25
bfi10_agreeableness	BFI-10: Agreeableness	Trait	Yes		1.22

Name	Label	Kind / type of concept	Incl.	RfE	VIF
bfi10_conscientiousness	BFI-10: Conscientiousness	Trait	Yes		1.30
bfi10_neuroticism	BFI-10: Neuroticism	Trait	Yes		1.32
PVQ_self_transcendence	PVQ-R: Self-Transcendence	Value	Yes		2.17
PVQ_self_enhancement	PVQ-R: Self-Enhancement	Value	Yes		1.51
PVQ_openness_to_change	PVQ-R: Openness to Change	Value	Yes		1.93
PVQ_conservation	PVQ-R: Conservation	Value	Yes		1.55
PANAS_positive	PANAS: Positive affect	trait	Yes		1.80
PANAS_negative	PANAS: Negative affect	Trait	Yes		1.42
NEP_efa_score1	NEP: Human impact on precious environment	Attitude	Yes		2.28
NEP_efa_score2	NEP: Right to exploitation	Attitude	Yes		2.37
migration_background	Migration background	Sociodemographic	Yes		1.30
organic_food_shopping	Motivation to Purchase Organic Food	Purchase Intention and Behaviour	Yes		1.52
worried	Worried about economic situation	Quality of life	Yes		2.46
general_satisfaction	General satisfaction	Trait	Yes		1.61
env_haz	Affected by pollution	Quality of life	Yes		1.39

Note: Incl. = feature included as predictor in modelling process; RfE = Reasons for Exclusion, only if not included: E: item was removal was erroneous; M: item was measured multiple, excluded item was not the latest; NA: too many missing values; O: item was removed due to theoretical considerations; S: item was used to derive another item during preprocessing; T: item was measured after the outcome; VIF = variance inflation factor